

Grain quality

Calorific values of 60 rice varieties

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We determined the calorific values of 60 rice varieties (30 hybrid derivatives, 28 traditional, and 2 improved varieties) in raw and parboiled forms (see table).

Calories significantly differed among the varieties. In raw rice, traditional variety Aryankali had the highest value (371 kcal) and the hybrid derivative Bhadra, the lowest (279 kcal). We observed a significant variation in calories in all rice

varieties after parboiling, with Aryankali again having the highest calorific value

(383 kcal) and Bhadra, the lowest (301 kcal). ■

Calorific values of 60 rice varieties.

Variety	Raw rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Parboiled rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Variety	Raw rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Parboiled rice (kcal g ⁻¹)
Kavungin-poothala	330	357	Thrissur local 2	312	333
Veluthavattan	317	337	Ponnaryan	332	348
Kattamodan	342	380	Chuvannari Thavalakannan	336	356
Arvan	345	375	Veluthari Thavalakannan	346	359
Vadakken Chitteni	307	358	Thkkencheera	357	365
Thekken	345	353	Cheriya Aryan	316	364
Chenkayama	342	345	Aruvakkari	348	354
Chuvannamodan	321	329	Kutticheradi	344	356
Elappapoochemban	335	372	Sinduram	316	373
Navara	341	358	<i>Improved</i>		
Thrissur local 1	312	333	CO 25	341	358
			Mashuri	332	362

Cibodas, a high-yielding variety with good grain quality

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B9775b-Mr-8-1-1 (derived from the cross B7004d-Mr-10-1/B6992f-Mr-262) is a

high-yielding line with good grain quality. Released as Cibodas for the irrigated rice ecosystem in Sep 1995, the variety is resistant to brown planthopper biotype 1 and bacterial blight strain III. It yields about 30% more than IR64 and Cisadane at 200- to 500-m above sea level (Table 1). Cibodas seems more suitable for cropping on intermediate elevation (about 400 m).

We compared grain quality characteristics of Cibodas with those of IR64 and Cisadane (Table 2). Large grain size (1,000-grain weight = 349) probably contributes to the variety's high yield potential. Cibodas has intermediate amylose content and tender cooking quality that rice consumers in Java prefer. ■

Table 1. Average yield of Cibodas in seven provinces in Indonesia. 1993-95.

Province	Locations (no.)	Elevation (m)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over check (%) ^a
Jakarta	1	50	5.7	2 a
West Java	3	200-450	8.2	30 b
West Java	3	400-600	7.0	29 a
Central Java	3	2-18	5.8	12 a
East Java	1	86	6.2	5 a
Lampung	1	750	6.3	14 a
Bengkulu	1	320	6.9	12 a

^a a = IR64, b = Cisadane.

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics of Cibodas, IR64, and Cisadane.

Characteristic	Cibodas	IR64	Cisadane
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.7 - 8.2	3.8 - 6.2	4.8 - 7.8
Plant height (cm)	115	99	110
Days to maturity	123	115	135
1,000-grain weight (g)	34	25	28
Head rice recovery (%)	80	80	80
Grain length (mm)	6.5	7.0	6.7
Grain length-breadth ratio	2.4	3.2	2.6
Amylose content	24	22	20
Cooking quality	Tender	Tender	Tender

Improving provitamin A (carotenoid) content of rice endosperm

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Genetic engineering is a feasible approach to alter or improve carotenoid content of endosperm, an agronomically valuable tissue. However, to plan a strategy for engineering rice endosperm, we must identify the biosynthetic block preventing carotenoid accumulation. Three alternative possibilities are being considered: 1) genes encoding one or more of the biosynthetic enzymes may not be expressed in the endosperm, 2) these enzymes are expressed but are not functional, and/or 3) a limitation